

SUBSTANCES AROUND US

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Annotation. Every day we come across a huge amount of substances and don't even think about where and what substances, the substances used, what formula does sugar or table salt have? The article examines the surrounding substances, their chemical formulas, as well as their use in cooking, construction, medicine, agriculture science, cosmetology.

Key words: chemistry, substances, everyday life, cooking, cosmetology, construction, agriculture farming, medicine.

The famous scientist Linus Pauling wrote: "Science plays such an important role in modern life, that no person without scientific knowledge can correctly understand the world in which he lives." From the time of science, including chemistry, explains many natural phenomena and production processes. Chemical substances are widely used in cooking, construction science, medicine, agriculture, cosmetology.

In cooking

Baking soda (NaHCO_3) - used in cooking - acts as a leavening agent in dough, which is activated when connection with an acid-containing substance. Soda part of human blood, and it is its taste that we feel We forgive when we bring the wound to our lips [1].

Rock salt (NaCl) - used to obtain salt, soda, etc. Used as a flavoring owl food additive. On average, every person per year consumes 8 kg of salt [1].

Iodized salt (KIO_3) is table salt, containing a certain amount of iodine salts. Is used as a flavoring additive in food, and also for the prevention of iodine deficiency diseases [1].

Water (H_2O) is a clear liquid with no taste and smell. Can be used in almost all preparations dishes and drinks. Hot water turns faster into ice than cold [1].

Carbon dioxide (CO_2) is a colorless gas. Use used in the production of soda and carbonated drinks [3].

Dry ice is a solid state of carbon dioxide, under normal conditions it goes into a gaseous state - tion, bypassing liquid (sublimation) [2].

Sugar ($C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$) - used as an additive in confectionery Terek products, and in large quantities as a preservative. Sugar is divided into cane and beet sugar. In the middle centuries, sugar was considered a medicine and was sold in pharmacies [1].

Acetic acid ($C_2H_4O_2$) is a colorless liquid, with a pungent odor used in canning food ducts Every day a person excretes about 400 g of vinegar [1].

In construction

Calcium oxide (CaO) is a white solid used for the manufacture of porcelain, as well as in the manufacture preparing cement. Calcium oxide is used in prosugar production [1].

Calcium hydroxide ($Ca(OH)_2$) is a white substance color obtained by combining water and oxide calcium. Used in construction as a binder substance. The use of lime milk is very widespread, for example, in the food industry changes as a food additive - E526 [1].

Sulfur (S) is a yellow flammable substance used to create sulfur asphalt that covers everything modern roads. When sulfur burns it releases gas (SO_2), which was used in ancient times as poisons from pests [2].

Methane (CH_4) is a tasteless, clear gas that used as fuel for cars and rockets. Water may freeze at a temperature of $+20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ if it there is methane [1].

Silicon dioxide (SiO₂) - used in the production production of glass, concrete products, ceramics, etc. but (SiO₂) is placed in small bags in clothes and shoes, to absorb moisture [2].

Potash (K₂CO₃) is a low-toxic white crystalline chemical substance used in the manufacture of glass, dyes and as an antifreeze additive. By tash is used to create liquid soap [1].

Magnesium oxide (MgO) - used in the production rubber, cement, for purification of petroleum products, as well as for the manufacture of refractory bricks. Oxide magnesium is used to extinguish fires [1].

Marble (CaCO₃) - used as a building material material, and is also used for making memory nicks, monumental sculptures and mosaics. Marble very resistant to heat, which is why the most expensive fireplaces made of marble [1].

Ammonia (NH₄Cl) - used in mechanical engineering - research, in the textile industry, when soldering metal fishing, etc. In nature, ammonia can be found in volcanic rocks in caves and near cracks in the ground [1].

In medicine

Potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) - used as disinfectant for treating wounds and burns gov. Potassium permanganate is a very strong oxidizing agent, its use used when bleaching fabrics and photographs [1].

Oxygen (O₂) - in hospitals it is stored in cylinders nah and is used for breathing problems, as oxygen mask. Oxygen is the second most active non-metal, because it very actively enters into chemical ical reactions [1].

Boric acid B(OH)₃ - used in medicine, as an antimicrobial antiseptic. Boronic acid can be found in nature in the mineral sassolin, in hot springs and mineral waters [1].

Activated carbon (C) - taken orally for food poisoning, as well as allergies. Acticharcoal is widely used in cosmetology, it is added to masks and scrubs to cleanse the skin [1].

Glucose (C₆H₁₂O₆) - in medicine administered orally for food poisoning or infections. Usage Available in the form of powder, solution and tablets. After winter her hibernating frogs thaw and come to life, this happens walks due to increased blood glucose levels amphibian [1].

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) - a solution in medicine hydrogen peroxide with water is used as an antiseptic a medicinal product for treating wounds and burns. Thanks to peroxide has strong oxidizing properties used in textile production and manufacturing paper [2].

Ammonia (NH₃·H₂O) – colorless liquid with a strong odor. In medicine it is used yut, in order to return a person from fainting condition. Vapors from ammonia can change colors, for example, blues become green or red [1].

Iodine (I₂) is used as a disinfectant quality, in the production of bactericidal and antiseptic means in pharmaceuticals as tincture and iodoform. Iodine in tablets it is used to purify drinking water [3].

In cosmetology

Glycerin (C₃H₈O₃) - used in cosmetology as a softening and moisturizing element. Glycerol used during the preparation of pasta, bread, sweets and processing of dried fruits [1].

Acetone (CH₃)₂CO is one of the most diffused with a solvent, in cosmetology it is used Used to remove nail polish. In the human body. When acetone is released and leaves naturally [1].

Ozone (O₃) - used to treat various diseases metological problems, for example, moisturizes and nourishes skin, as well as when treating the skin with ozone, regenerate cells. Ozone is a strong oxidizing agent and is used is used for disinfection of air and water [1].

In agriculture

Ammonia (NH₃) - mainly used to create of nitrogen fertilizers. Of all types of fertilizers, nitrogen is They best nourish the soil [1].

Ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3) is one of the most common types of nitrogen fertilizers. Excess of convenience rhenium can lead to chemical burn of leaves [2].

Calcium phosphate ($\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$) is mainly used used as phosphate fertilizers. Calcium phosphate tion is also used as a food additive for preparing bread, for feeding livestock and birds [2].

Conclusion

Based on my analysis of the literature, based on the data, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- substances surround us every day;
- the substances are very different and not similar to each other.

LITERATURE:

1. Chemical encyclopedia. - M.: Soviet Encyclopedia. 1988. - Text: electronic // TSB: [website]. — URL: <https://rus-chemical-enc.slovaronline.com/>(access date: 02/06/2023).
2. Wikipedia.-Text: electronic//Wikipedia: [site]. -URL: <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia> (date access: 02/06/2023).
3. Chemistry. Encyclopedia / trans. from English S. Temirkhanova. - Astana: Publishing House "Foliant", 2012. - 160 p.